

Athletic Injuries: Comparison by Team and Individual Sports

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Received Apr 02, 2018; Accepted Apr 16, 2018; Published Apr 16, 2018

Abstract

Injury occurred at the All India University and National Championship was surveyed. The data on injury was surveyed from 300 sportspersons of various team and individual sports. The mean of the age was 20.32 years with a peak 17 to 28 year's age group. Abrasion is the highest frequent injury in team game where as Muscle pull is in individual games. Second highest injury in team games was Sprain and Contusion in individual games. Meniscus tear, ligament rupture, fracture, concussion and dislocation are most severe injuries found in various types of team and individual sports. Most of the injuries are minor, and moderate. Severe injuries are closely associated with highly stressful body contact and team sports such as, Boxing, Wrestling, Gymnastic, Basketball, Hockey, Football and Kabaddi.

Key Words: Sports Injury, Survey, Team Game, Individual Game.

1. Introduction:

Sports injuries are injuries which occur during sports activity or exercise. In India due to the lack of sufficient facilities many sportsperson get injured during training of competition. These injuries can be prevented by to provide them adequate knowledge of injury pattern or mechanism. The causes in the body where numbness and shivering happens upon sports wounds are generally the primary indications of the body revealing to you that the body was affected. In this manner, when a competitor whines of numbness and particularly shivering, the way to a conclusion is to get a point by point history of the competitor's obtained side effect observation, decide the impact the damage had on the body and its procedures, and after that set up the prime treatment strategy. In the process to figure out what precisely occurred in the body and the standing impacts most therapeutic experts pick a strategy for mechanical medicinal gadgets to secure a tenable answer for the site of damage. Anticipation lessens potential game wounds. It is imperative to set up cooperation in warm-ups, extending, and practices that attention on principle muscle bunches regularly utilized as a part of the game of intrigue. Additionally, making damage aversion program as a group, which incorporates training on rehydration, sustenance, checking colleagues "in danger", observing conduct, abilities, and procedures.

2. Materials & Methods:

The present study has been designed to investigate injury pattern between team and individual sports. The following procedure has been adapted to fulfillment this study requirement:

2.1 Selection of the Samples:

A total 300 sportspersons were surveyed for collect the data of injuries. 150 players were from team game and rest of from individual games. The age of the selected sample were ranged from 17-28 years. The injury data were drawn from All India University or National Championship.

2.2.1 Selection of the Variables:

A well-structured open ended injury report form was used to collect the information related to injuries which include the follow variables:

- Demographic information of the respondents.
- Common injuries
- Body parts associated and
- Injury reasons (intrinsic & extrinsic).

2.3 Data Collection:

Data were collected during university or national championships held at different universities of India. For accuracy of the data each injury incidence were recorded after the evaluation of a physiotherapist present at time of competition. Each injury reports form were filled by the researcher after consult with the present physiotherapist.

2.4 Statistical Tools:

Descriptive statistics, mean standard deviation were used to explore the characteristics of selected sample. Percentage method was used to distribute the injury occurrence between team and individual sports. Chi-square also called the test of independence was used to find out the association between injuries and sports type. Graph and tables were also used to illustrate the data characteristics.

3. Results of the Study:

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-1 Characteristics of Sample

Game Type		Age	Height	Weight	Experience (Years)	Training Hours
Team game	N	150	150	150	150	150
	Mean	20.59	173.2954	68.49	6.34	4.15
	SEM	.181	.59076	.868	.228	.088
	SD	2.236	7.28340	10.698	2.815	1.086
	Minimum	17	152.40	34	1	2
	Maximum	29	198.12	100	7	6
Individual Game	N	150	150	150	150	150
	Mean	20.04	173.5212	72.29	4.83	4.34
	SEM	.256	.67511	1.270	.285	.075
	SD	3.119	8.21303	15.450	3.467	.916
	Minimum	15	144.78	42	1	2
	Maximum	33	195.58	130	6	8

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-2 Distribution of Common injuries in Team Games

		Responses		Injury Rate	Injury Ranking
		N	Percent		
Injuries	ABRASION	83	15.6%	55.7%	1
	BLISTERS	29	5.5%	19.5%	9
	CONTUSION	56	10.5%	37.6%	4
	INCISION	26	4.9%	17.4%	10
	LACERATION	23	4.3%	15.4%	11
	DISLOCATION	17	3.2%	11.4%	12
	FRACTURE	41	7.7%	27.5%	5
	LIGAMENT BREAK	29	5.5%	19.5%	9
	MUSCLE CRAMP	34	6.4%	22.8%	7
	MUSCLE PULL	57	10.7%	38.3%	3
	PUNCTURE WOUND	3	0.6%	2.0%	19
	SPRAIN	67	12.6%	45.0%	2
	STRAIN	35	6.6%	23.5%	6
	TENDINITIES	5	0.9%	3.4%	16
	CONCUSSION	4	0.8%	2.7%	17
	MENISCUS TEAR	6	1.1%	4.0%	14
	TENNIS ELBOW	5	0.9%	3.4%	16
	BACK PAIN	3	0.6%	2.0%	19
	MUSCLE TEAR	2	0.4%	1.3%	20
ROTATOR CUFF	7	1.3%	4.7%	13	
Total		532	100.0%	357.0%	

- Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.
- Percentage of Injury rate per 100 athletes.
- Injury Ranking (1st rank denote highest score) (based on injury rate)
- Ranks are in descending order

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-3 Distribution of Common injuries in Individual Games

		Responses		Injury Rate	Injury Ranking
		N	Percent		
injuries	ABRASION	33	9.1%	22.4%	6
	BLISTERS	23	6.3%	15.6%	9
	CONTUSION	45	12.4%	30.6%	2
	INCISION	14	3.8%	9.5%	11
	LACRATION	7	1.9%	4.8%	12
	DISLOCATION	25	6.9%	17.0%	7
	FRACTURE	36	9.9%	24.5%	4
	LIGAMENT BREAK	23	6.3%	15.6%	9
	MUSCLE CRAMP	33	9.1%	22.4%	6
	MUSCLE PULL	50	13.7%	34.0%	1
	SPRAIN	36	9.9%	24.5%	4
	STRAIN	22	6.0%	15.0%	10
	TENDINITIES	1	0.3%	0.7%	18
	MINUSCUS TEAR	2	0.5%	1.4%	17
	TENNIS ELBOW	3	0.8%	2.0%	15
	BACK PAIN	5	1.4%	3.4%	13
	SHIN PAIN	3	0.8%	2.0%	15
	ROTATOR CUFF	3	0.8%	2.0%	15
Total		364	100.0%	247.6%	

- Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.
- Percentage of Injury rate per 100 athletes.
- Injury Ranking (1st rank denote highest score) (based on injury rate)
- Ranks are in descending order

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.-4 Chi-square Table

Sr.No.	(Injuries)	(df)	(χ^2)	Asymp.sig.
1	Abrasion	1	31.539	.000
2	Blisters	1	.655	.418
3	Contusion	1	1.109	.292
4	Incision	1	8.518	.004
5	Laceration	1	9.015	.003
6	Dislocation	1	2.448	.115
7	Fracture	1	.276	.599
8	Ligament Rupture	1	.655	.418
9	Muscle Cramp	1	.000	.988
10	Muscle Pull	1	.301	.583
11	Puncture wound	1	2.951	.086
12	Sprain	1	12.980	.000
13	Strain	1	4.263	.039
14	Tendonitis	1	2.614	.106
15	Concussion	1	3.947	.047
16	Meniscus tear	1	1.947	.163
17	Low Back Pain	1	1.115	.291
18	Muscle Tear	1	1.960	.161
19	Rotator cuff	1	1.547	.214

The table 3-4 shows the association between injuries and game type. It was observed that association between Abrasion, Incision, Laceration, Sprain, Strain and Concussion and game type is high the value of χ^2 is higher than the table value. It shows that occurrence of these injuries and game types are not independent. In simple words we can says that these significant injuries have the higher probability of occurrence in team games in comparison of individual games.

4. Conclusions:

After analysis the tables given above it was observed that Abrasion is the highest frequent injury in team game where as Muscle pull is in individual games. Second highest injury in team games was Sprain and Contusion in individual games. Meniscus tear, ligament rupture, fracture, concussion and dislocation are most severe injuries found in various types of team and individual sports. Most of the injuries are minor, and moderate. Severe injuries are closely associated with highly stressful body contact and team sports such as, Boxing, Wrestling, Gymnastic, Basketball, Hockey, Football and Kabaddi.

5. Recommendations:

This study conducted between team and individual sports competition. It is hoped that all the sports departments in India should come forward to adopt sports injury reporting system for documentation and for future research. Information about the occurrences, nature of sports injuries and consciousness is the main product of injury surveillance. Injury surveillance is the first step in classifying the problem. Surveillance of injuries also helps in recognizing the cause of injuries so that injury prevention dealings can be developed as an intervention. This will permit for some injuries to be prevented. It is hoped that the coaches, administrators should appliance sports injury data collection system in their establishments that will help to develop injury prevention methodologies in all sports.

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